



Site 1A (35.357677 N, 106.716265 W)



Site 1B (35.346564 N, 106.765519 W)



Site 1C (35.349047 N, 106.788465 W)



Site 1E (35.375429 N, 106.768261 W)



Site 1F (35.367414 N, 106.743505 W)



Site 1H (35.392188 N, 106.755195 W)



Site 1I (35.39211 N, 106.775899 W)



Site 2A (35.274065 N, 106.730801 W)



Site 2B (35.25801 N, 106.758379 W)



Site 2C (35.275358 N, 106.803184 W)



Site 2D (35.290763 N, 106.784133 W)



Site 2E (35.29078 N, 106.754997 W)



Site 2F (35.293681 N, 106.729184 W)



Site 2G (35.318671 N, 106.731998 W)



Site 2H (35.320086 N, 106.759967 W)



Site 2I (35.319824 N, 106.785113 W)



Site 3A (35.2682 N, 106.62683 W)



Site 3B (35.258328 N, 106.666786 W)



Site 3C (35.256674 N, 106.697474 W)



Site 3D (35.281627 N, 106.698731 W)



Site 3E (35.290792 N, 106.657471 W)



Site 3F (35.306312 N, 106.629105 W)



Site 3G (35.322982 N, 106.636651 W)



Site 3H (35.324514 N, 106.666128 W)



Site 3I (35.326153 N, 106.696324 W)